

Local Extrema of apparent brightness of Ceres, Pallas, Juno and Vesta seen from Mars

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An observer stays in a space ship that circles round the Mars.

Explanation: mag= stellar magnitude, °= deg , '= angular minute, " = angular second
AE = astronomical unit = 149598500 km

Ceres seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance Mars - Ceres in AE	Distance Ceres-sun in AE
25.3.-10.4. 2017	+7.06	1.03	1.27	2.74-2.77 decreasing
28.4.-26.6. 2019	+9.62	0.32-0.33 increasing	3.96-4.09 decreasing	2.74-2.80 increasing

Pallas seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance Mars - Pallas in AE	Distance Pallas-sun in AE
5.7.-9.8. 2017	+10.01	0.20-0.21 decreasing	3.55-3.69 increasing	2.74-2.83 decreasing
25.6.-6.8. 2018	+9.23	0.21-0.22 decreasing	3.41-3.45 increasing	2.13-2.14 decreasing

Juno seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance Mars - Juno in AE	Distance Juno - sun in AE
3.3.-22.4. 2017	+11.67	0.068-0.070 decreasing	4.57-4.69 increasing	3.19-3.26 decreasing
10.6.-25.6 2019	+7.18	0.407-0.412 increasing	0.78-0.79 decreasing	2.30-2.35 increasing

Vesta seen from Mars:

Date	Apparent brightness [mag]	Apparent diameter ["]	Distance Mars - Vesta in AE	Distance Vesta - sun in AE
10.4.-23.4 2018	+4.41	1.09-1.11 decreasing	0.66-0.67 increasing	2.15-2.16 decreasing
14.1.-27.2. 2020	+8.72	0.17-0.18 decreasing	4.05-4.08 increasing	2.56-2.58 increasing

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